

ProteoForce

D1.1 Data management plan

Name of project: Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients

Code: 09I03-03-V03-00008

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Name of project: Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients (Proteo Force)

No. 09I03-03-V03-00008

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Author(s):	Mgr. Ondrej Ragač, Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.
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APPROVALS

Task leader: Mgr. Ondrej Ragač
 WP leader: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.
 Project coordinator: Assoc. prof. RNDr. Gabriel Žoldák, DrSc.

Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the authors.

ABBREVIATIONS

AAM/VoR	Author accepted manuscript/version of record (VOR)
API	Application Programming Interface
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoS attack	Denial-of-service attack
DoW	The Description of Work
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	The European Research Area
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
I4OC	Initiative for Open Citations
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	European Open Science Infrastructure, for open scholarly and scientific communication.
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange
PDF	Portable Data File
PID	A persistent identifier
PMC	PubMed Central®
UI	User Interface
UPJS	Univerzita Pavla Jozefa Šafárika v Košiciach
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

SUMMARY

The ProteoForce Data Management Plan (DMP) (1.1 version) is presented here, which delineates the data handling processes that will be implemented throughout the project. Throughout the duration of the project, ProteoForce generates a variety of data types that are stored. We will aid with the storage and reusability of the project data following the project's conclusion. We have determined that the Zenodo repository platform will be the repository for data storage, as it meets the mandatory and highly recommended criteria for data repositories.

The ProteoForce project is involved in a pilot initiative that focuses on open research data. The objective is to offer guidance on the types of data that the project will collect, the methods by which the data will be preserved, and the sharing policies that will be implemented to ensure that the research community has easy access to the data. The following issues are specifically addressed in the project's efforts to address open research data:

- (i) the types of open and non-open data that will be generated or collected by researchers through experimental work and research related to the project;
- (ii) the standards used to encrypt the data;
- (iii) the technologies and infrastructures used to preserve the data long-term securely; and
- (iv) the sharing/access policies that are applied to each dataset. The plan serves as a benchmark for the allocation of resources and budgets related to data management, as well as a blueprint for the future.

The current DMP will be upgraded in accordance with the project's requirements as the project progresses. The current state of data management, utilization, and protection of rights and results will be reflected in the DMP.

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1. INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

One of the anticipated effects is the facilitation of unrestricted access and reuse of research data. In order to achieve this objective, two main methods are employed: 1) Creating a Data Management Plan (DMP), and 2) Facilitating unrestricted access to research data for the general public.

To achieve the objectives of the project, the project coordinator must complete various specific tasks. These tasks include creating the Data Management Plan (DMP), regularly updating the DMP, depositing data in a repository, facilitating access to the data for other researchers and the public, and providing necessary background information for working with the primary data. The Pilot primarily focuses on two main elements:

- The necessary data (including metadata) needed to verify the results presented in scientific publications.
- Additional carefully selected and/or unprocessed data, including information about the data itself

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will serve as a comprehensive document that will ensure effective data management throughout the entire duration of the project. Its purpose is to ensure that the information collected and generated during the project is easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, following the FAIR principles.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the procedures for managing the data generated by the ProteoForce project during and after its completion. The Data Management Plan (DMP) establishes protocols and essential criteria for the collection, storage, analysis, and systematic dissemination of data in accordance with the FAIR principles. The DMP for the ProteoForce project was initially conceptualized as a "living document" and will be periodically revised as needed. The authors of the DMP will establish certain standards, folder structure, and identifiers. Information will be disseminated through the internal information channels and discussed in the regular group meetings. The leader of WP1 Task 1.1 will oversee and manage all communication.

1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

A general objective of the ProteoForce project is to significantly strengthen the scientific excellence in protein science at the University of Pavol Jozef Safarik in Kosice by establishing a pioneering laboratory dealing with single-molecule force spectroscopy, with a focus on clinically relevant protein targets, such as Hsp70, androgen receptors, and membrane proteins. The project aims to advance scientific research in the field of medical research and contribute positively to the socio-economic landscape of Slovakia, aligning with the domains of “Innovative industry for the 21st century” and “a healthy society.”

The following main objectives of the project will be reached:

- (1) Develop an advanced single-molecule laser optical tweezers force laboratory in Slovakia.** The functionality and adequacy of the laboratory will be evaluated based on the successful execution of initial force spectroscopy experiments. These experiments will demonstrate the capabilities of the advanced single-molecule laser optical tweezers force laboratory. The evaluation will focus on the laboratory's ability to precisely manipulate molecules, conduct correlative quantitative measurements, and study molecular interactions with high precision and accuracy. The evaluation process will involve conducting a series of force spectroscopy experiments using the newly established laboratory setup. The outcomes of these experiments will be analyzed, and the performance of the laboratory will be assessed against predefined criteria for accuracy, reproducibility, and reliability. Any deviations or adjustments needed to optimize the laboratory's performance will be identified and addressed during the evaluation process.
- (2) Promote open science principles and data sharing.** To evaluate the success of promoting open science principles and data sharing, the project will monitor compliance with the PQP, DMP, and open-access policies. The availability and reproducibility of research findings will be assessed to ensure adherence to open science standards.
- (3) Incorporate high-risk and low-risk research questions.** The achievement of this objective will be evaluated through an assessment of the project's research outputs and publications addressing both high-risk and low-risk questions. The outcomes of tasks, exploring different types of research questions, will be analyzed to determine the project's willingness to pursue potentially ground-breaking scientific inquiries while also generating potentially highly exciting results.

(4) Investigating Clinically Relevant Proteins with Hsp70 Chaperones

The successful design and implementation of experiments to study molecular forces in proteins - preparing and modifying proteins for laser optical tweezers, will be considered a low-risk research question. The inclusion of this task and its completion will verify the project's effort to explore clinically relevant proteins with Hsp70 chaperones.

(5) Interaction of Membrane Proteins with Hsp70 Chaperones.

The development and implementation of novel approaches based on nanodisc technology and the incorporation of functional membrane proteins - preparing and modifying proteins for laser optical tweezers, will be considered a high-risk research question. The inclusion of this task and its execution will verify the project's efforts to explore pioneering research related to the interaction of membrane proteins with Hsp70 chaperones.

The achievement of this objective will be evaluated based on the successful observation and analysis of molecular forces in membrane proteins and the ability to conduct experiments on membrane proteins with Hsp70 chaperones will indicate progress in exploring pioneering research. Additionally, the results will be published in peer-reviewed journals.

(6) Publish high-quality research papers and secure funding

Consistent submission of research papers to reputable journals and funding proposals. Clinically relevant protein clients under load in the presence of Hsp70 and Task 2.3 - Grant submission to Horizon Europe and national resources, will verify the project's progress toward achieving this objective. The successful submission and documentation of research papers and grant proposals in the respective deliverables will confirm the project's efforts in pursuing high-quality research publications and securing funding.

The achievement of this objective will be evaluated through the publication of research papers in high-quality peer-reviewed journals. The successful acceptance and publication of research findings in reputable journals will demonstrate the project's ability to produce high-quality research papers. Also, the successful submission and approval of grant proposals.

(7) Foster collaborations and knowledge exchange within Slovakia

The establishment of collaborations with national stakeholders and research institutions will be verified through the project's involvement in Task - Identification and Initiation of Collaborations. This task aims to identify potential collaborators, initiate calls and video conferences to define research avenues, and establish collaborations with renowned research groups in Bratislava working on tau protein and Hsp70 substrates.

The achievement of the objective will be evaluated by assessing the frequency and quality of knowledge exchange activities and publications resulting from the established collaborations. Effective Collaboration as the Result of Networking Activity involves conducting joint research with partners, providing data analysis, and submitting manuscripts to prestigious journals. The impact of these collaborations on knowledge dissemination, knowledge exchange events, and resulting publications will demonstrate the success of this objective.

(8) Contribute to the national and European research landscape

The project's participation in national and European research events and collaborations will indicate progress toward achieving the objective. Attendance of Conferences aims to proactively coordinate the project team's involvement in conferences and seminars, including those organized by prominent European societies such as EBSA, FEBS, and EMBO. Completed Conference Attendances (10x), will verify the project's active engagement in research events at both national and European levels.

For **each objective**, specific requirements of data collection/generation are needed and are reported in the table below.

Table 1.

MAIN OBJECTIVES	DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION	WP
1) SO1. Develop an advanced single-molecule laser optical tweezers force laboratory in Slovakia. SO2. Promote open science principles and data sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 1.1. Quality assurance and risk management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D1.1 Data Management Plan and Project Quality Plan • Task 1.2 Interim Report <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D1.2 Interim report • Task 1.3 Lab Installation and research on bio-constructs for optical tweezers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D1.3 Procurement documents and report • Task 1.4 Final Report <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D1.4 Procurement documents and the final report 	WP1
2) SO3. Incorporate high-risk and low-risk research questions SO4. Explore Pioneering Research #1: Investigating Clinically Relevant Proteins with Hsp70 Chaperones SO5. Explore Pioneering Research #2: interaction of membrane proteins with Hsp70 chaperones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 2.1. Preparing and modifying proteins for laser optical tweezers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D2.1 Proteins for tweezers, Report • Task 2.2 Clinically relevant protein clients under load in the presence of Hsp70 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D2.2 Chaperone microfluidics – Publications • Task 2.3 Grant submissions to Horizon Europe and national resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D2.3 submitted grants to HE and national calls, reported in D1.3 Final Report 	WP2

SO6. Publish high-quality research papers and secure funding		
3) SO7. Foster collaborations and knowledge exchange within Slovakia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 3.1. Identification and initiation of collaborations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D3.1 Interim Networking Activity will be described in D1.2 Interim Report • Task 3.2 Training and research internships for early-stage researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D3.2 Training activity completed and described in D1.4 Final Report • Task 3.3 Effective national collaboration as the result of networking activity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D3.3 Networking activity will be described in D1.4 Final Report 	WP3
4) SO8. Contribute to the national and European research landscape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 4.1. Research on Hsp70 targets with international collaboration partner and preparing communication plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D4.1 Joint research activities with international partner and communication Plan and will be presented in D1.2 Interim Report • Task 4.2 Attendance of conferences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D4.2 Completed attendances of conferences (10x), which will be summarized and described in D1.4 Final Report • Task 4.3 Summarising dissemination and communication activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ D4.3 Summary of Communication and Dissemination will be described in D1.4 Final Report 	WP4

1.2 What types of data will the project generate/collect?

ProteoForce objectives will produce text data with embedded images from secondary sources (see Table 1). At the same time, ProteoForce will exploit existing data and integrate them with new data. Table 1 shows the primary data on which it will exploit.

1.3 What formats of data will the project generate/collect?

By default, data will be stored in Portable Data File (pdf) format. Database, notes, and other data can be stored in other formats that are readable by MS Office tools and their open versions.

1.4 What is the origin of the data?

Data are from both primary and secondary sources.

1.5 What is the expected size of the data?

The expected overall data size is approx. 1000 GB. Can be extended according to the project needs.

1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Data utility is summarized in the following Table.

Table 2. Data primarily generated by the ProteoForce project. *Text with embedded images

DATA	TYPE/FORMAT	TARGET GROUPS	AVAILABILITY
Original research publications or accepted manuscripts	Text*/pdf	Researchers	Open access as much as possible / limited by the funding sources
Quality assurance and risk management	Text*/pdf	Project members/grant agency/public	Confidential
Interim reports	Text*/pdf	Researchers/grant agencies	Confidential
Lab Installation and research on bio-constructs for optical tweezers	Text*/pdf	Ph.D. students	Free
Preparing and modifying proteins for laser optical tweezers	Text*/pdf	PhD. students	Free/open access publications
Clinically relevant protein clients under load in the presence of Hsp70	Text*/pdf	Ph.D. students	Free/confidential if potential IPR
Training and research internships for early-stage researchers	Text*/pdf	Ph.D. students	Free
Presentations, Posters	Text*/pdf	Researchers, public	Free/confidential if potential IPR
Effective national collaboration as the result of networking activity	Text*/pdf	Project members/grant agency/public	Confidential/free based on partners agreements
Project quality plan	Text*/pdf	Project members/grant agency/public	Free
Data management plan	Text*/pdf	Project members/grant agency/public	Free

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

We have chosen Zenodo as the platform for our repository. Zenodo is a versatile open-access repository that was created as part of the European OpenAIRE program and is currently managed by CERN. Researchers can upload research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and other digital artifacts related to their research. A unique digital object identifier (DOI) is created for every submission, ensuring that the stored items can be easily cited. Zenodo adheres to the FAIR principles.

In order to achieve findability:

F1: (meta)data are given a universally distinct and enduring identifier

- A DOI is assigned to each published record on Zenodo.
- The data on Zenodo are described using comprehensive metadata, as defined by R1.
- Zenodo's metadata adheres to the minimum and recommended terms of DataCite's Metadata Schema, with some additional enhancements.

F3: The metadata unambiguously and specifically contains the identifier of the data it is describing.

The DOI is an essential and obligatory element in the metadata of every record.

F4: (meta)data are recorded or cataloged in a searchable repository

- The metadata of each record is promptly indexed and made searchable in Zenodo's search engine upon publication.
- The metadata of each record is transmitted to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

In order to be accessible:

A1: (Meta)data can be accessed by their unique identifier through a standardized communication protocol.

- The OAI-PMH protocol allows for the retrieval of metadata for individual records and collections by using the record identifier and the collection name.

Metadata can be obtained using the public REST API.

A1.1: The protocol is accessible, complimentary, and capable of being implemented universally.

Point A1 refers to the fact that OAI-PMH and REST are protocols that are open, free, and universally applicable for retrieving information on the web.

A1.2: The protocol enables an authentication and authorization procedure, if required.

- Metadata is openly available and licensed under the public domain. Retrieving it does not require any authorization.

A2: Metadata remains accessible even if the data itself becomes unavailable.

- The repository will retain both data and metadata indefinitely. The host laboratory CERN currently has a lifespan that extends for at least the next 20 years, during which it has a defined experimental program.

Metadata is stored in dedicated high-availability database servers at CERN, which are physically distinct from the actual data.

In order to achieve interoperability:

I1: (meta)data should be expressed in a formal, easily understandable, widely used language for representing knowledge. • Zenodo employs JSON Schema as an internal format for representing metadata and allows exporting to other commonly used formats like Dublin Core or MARCXML.

I2: The vocabularies used for (meta)data adhere to the FAIR principles.

- We consult open, external vocabularies for specific terms, such as license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef), and grants (OpenAIRE).

I3: The (meta)data contains precise references to other (meta)data that are qualified.

- Every mentioned external piece of metadata is accompanied by a resolvable URL.

In order to be reusable:

R1: The (meta)data is extensively described with multiple accurate and relevant attributes.

Each record includes at least the required terms specified by DataCite, and may also include additional terms recommended by DataCite and enrichments provided by Zenodo.

R1.1: The (meta)data is made available with a transparent and easily understandable data usage license.

- License is a compulsory requirement in Zenodo's metadata and pertains to an Open Definition license.
- Users who download the data are bound by the license stated in the metadata by the person who uploaded it.

R1.2: The (meta)data is linked to comprehensive information about its origin and history.

- All uploaded data and metadata can be traced back to a registered Zenodo user.
- Optionally, the metadata can provide information about the original authors of the published work.

R1.3: The (meta)data conforms to community standards that are relevant to the specific domain.

Zenodo is a repository that is not limited to a specific domain. However, it adheres to DataCite's Metadata Schema, which ensures that the metadata conforms to one of the most comprehensive standards across different domains.

Plan S - evaluation of adherence

The following Table is a self-assessment of Zenodo against the Plan S requirements for Open Access Repositories (as published October 2019). See the Plan S Principles and Implementation (under Part III: Technical Guidance and Requirements / 2. Requirements for Open Access Repositories).

Table 3. Mandatory (1-6) and strongly recommended (7-13) criteria for repositories vs. Zenodo

MANDATORY CRITERIA FOR REPOSITORIES		ZENODO
1. The repository must be registered in the Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) or in the process of being registered	✓	https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/2659
2. Use of PIDs for the deposited versions of the publications (with versioning, for example, in case of revisions), such as DOI (preferable), URN, or Handle.	✓	Zenodo registers DOIs (via DataCite) for all deposited records. See DataCite. Zenodo pioneered DOI versioning. Objects with pre-existing DOIs may be uploaded, and the external DOI displayed.
3. High-quality article-level metadata in a standard interoperable non-proprietary format, under a CC0 public domain dedication. This must include information on the DOI (or other PIDs) both of the original publication and the deposited version, on the version deposited (AAM/VoR), and	✓	High-quality article-level metadata.” Zenodo supports the DataCite Metadata Schema v4. The following additional article level fields are supported: journal title/volume/issue/pages, conference title/acronym/dates/place/website, book publisher/place/ISBN/title/pages, alternate persistent identifiers (see all fields).

<p>on the Open Access status and the license of the deposited version. Metadata must include complete and reliable information on funding provided by cOAlition S funders (including, as a minimum, the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier).</p>	<p>“in the standard interoperable non-proprietary format.”</p> <p>The following metadata formats are provided by Zenodo: MARCXML, Dublin Core (according to OpenAIRE Guidelines), DataCite, DCAT, JSON-LD (Schema.org).</p> <p>“under a CC0 public domain dedication.”</p> <p>All metadata in Zenodo may be freely used under the CC0 waiver. (see terms of use, bullet 7).</p> <p>“[...] include information on the DOI (or other PIDs) both of the original publication and the deposited version.”</p> <p>Zenodo registers DOIs for all uploads.</p> <p>Zenodo allows including information on alternate persistent identifiers, as well as linking to related persistent identifiers.</p> <p>“include [...] the Open Access status and the license of the deposited version.”</p> <p>All Zenodo records include the Open Access status according to the COAR access right vocabulary (open, embargoed, restricted, closed).</p> <p>All open access and embargoed records specify a license of the deposited material. Any license from the OpenDefinition and SPDX vocabularies are supported (including all Creative Commons licenses).</p> <p>“including as a minimum the name of the funder and the grant number/identifier.”</p> <p>All records can be uniquely linked to grants in the OpenAIRE grant database. The database currently covers 11 funders and 2 million grants.</p>
<p>4. Machine-readable information on the Open Access status and the license embedded in the article in a standard non-proprietary format.</p>	<p>✓ The open-access status and a license are embedded in all metadata formats (i.e., machine-readable). See our APIs below in the strongly recommended criteria response.</p> <p>It is the responsibility of the uploader to ensure the open access status and a license is embedded in any digital file uploaded. Zenodo does not modify files uploaded by users in any way.</p>
<p>5. Continuous availability (uptime at least 99.7%, not taking into account scheduled downtime for maintenance or upgrades).</p>	<p>✓ Zenodo publicly displays uptime on https://status.zenodo.org</p> <p>Historically Zenodo’s uptime is 99.98% (Oct 2019)</p>
<p>6. Helpdesk: as a minimum, an email address (functional mailbox)</p>	<p>✓ Zenodo provides support via https://zenodo.org/support</p>

<p>has to be provided; a response time of no more than one business day must be ensured.</p>		<p>The helpdesk is manned during CERN business hours (Mon-Fri 8:30-17:30 CET). Zenodo's average response time is 22 hours (based on 1534 requests received in the period May-Oct 2019, and not accounting for out-of-business hours).</p>
<p>7. Manuscript submission system that supports both individual author uploads and bulk uploads of manuscripts (AAM or VoR) by publishers.</p>	✓	<p>Zenodo supports users/machines uploading both AAM and VoR versions of manuscripts. Zenodo supports both author uploads via a normal deposit user interface as well as bulk uploads via our APIs.</p>
<p>8. Full text stored in a machine-readable community standard format such as JATS XML.</p>	✓	<p>Zenodo supports all file formats, consistent with the goal of accommodating all research objects. XML files are stored alongside other representations like PDF as just another format</p>
<p>9. Support for PIDs for authors (e.g., ORCID), funders, funding programs and grants, institutions, and other relevant entities.</p>	✓	<p>ORCID supported authors and contributors. Open Funder Registry supported funders. OpenAIRE grant database supported for grants. Zenodo plans to support ROR for institutions.</p>
<p>10. Openly accessible data on citations according to the standards by the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC).</p>	✓	<p>Zenodo supports linking records with related persistent identifiers (both incoming and outgoing links - i.e., citations and references). The links are exported in the DataCite metadata registered with the DOI, and thus makes the links available in the CrossRef/DataCite Event Data. Discovering citations to a record requires global knowledge of the entire world-wide corpus of journal articles which is out of scope for Zenodo. Zenodo, however, harvests openly available citation databases (Crossref/DataCite Event Data, NASA/SAO Astrophysics Data System, and Europe PMC) for citations to Zenodo objects. All citation data is exported in Scholix-format. See https://help.zenodo.org/#citations for details.</p>
<p>11. Open API to allow others (including machines) to access the content. A compliant API must be free to access without any barrier. A light authentication mechanism such as a token for 'power users' – e.g., high-traffic collaborators – is acceptable as long as there is a totally open/anonymous route too.</p>	✓	<p>Available APIs: OAI-PMH: https://zenodo.org/oai2d REST API: https://zenodo.org/api/records/ Documentation: https://developers.zenodo.org Zenodo allows anonymous and authenticated access (via OAuth 2.0 access token) to the API. All requests to Zenodo (both UI and API) are rate-limited to prevent abusive use and DoS attacks (default limit: 5000 request/hour). Zenodo's average request rate is 14 requests/second.</p>
<p>12. OpenAIRE compliance of the metadata.</p>	✓	<p>Zenodo is compliant with the OpenAIRE Guidelines v3.0.</p>

<p>13. Quality assurance processes to link full-text deposits with authoritative bibliographic metadata from third-party systems, e.g., PubMed, Crossref, or SCOPUS, where feasible</p>	✓	<p>Per community harvesting allows curation and indexing, e.g., NASA ADS harvests specific communities which are curated by astronomy librarians; similarly by ZHB Luzern, BLR, etc.</p>
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What naming conventions do you follow?

The general convention we will use is the following:

[WPx] [title] [year] [month] [verx] [.] ext

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

yes

Do you provide clear version numbers?

ProteoForce uses a workspace where the individual versions are registered within the accepted rules.

Data Items: specification of metadata

The following data items are foreseen to be generated at this stage:

- a. Reports: metadata are included at the beginning of the same file.
- b. Presentations: Metadata is included at the end of the same file.
- c. Multimedia data: Metadata is included at the end of the same file.

All ProteoForce reports will display the following information within their 1.-3. page:

Name of project: Establishing Slovakia’s First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients (ProteoForce), Project ID 09I03-03-V03-00008

Deliverable No:	
Work package no. and title:	
Task no. and title:	
Dissemination level:	
Lead Beneficiary:	
Author(s):	
Date of publication:	

Moreover, the file will report this sentence: This project has received funding from the Component 9 of the Recovery and Resilience Plan - Large projects for excellent

researchers. Code: 09I03-03-V03. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the authors.

Additionally, a sentence confirming compliance with the recent version of the DMP will be added.

Database

Databases will be made available in .xlsx format. Metadata will follow the Dublin Core format

[2]. Following items will be included: content, Intellectual, Property, Instantiation, Title, Creator, Date, Subject, Publisher, Format, Description, Contributor, Identifier, Type Rights, Language, Source, Relation, Coverage. If not applicable for a particular item, NA abbreviation will be used.

In the first sheet (metadata), the following metadata will be available if possible (based on Dublin Core Format):

CALL	Component 9 of the recovery and resilience plan
WORK PROGRAMME	Large projects for excellent researchers.
Project ID	09I03-03-V03-00008
Project web site	
Database type	Numeric, textual
Title	Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients
Creator	
Contributors	
Publisher	
Date	
Format	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Draft version n.	
Identifier	

Each database will be provided with information about structure and content, as follows. In some cases, information on the quality of the data will be provided.

FIELD LABEL	DESCRIPTION	TYPE (NUMERIC, TEXT, Y, N)	FORMAT

Presentations

General information: Name of the project, Abbreviation of the project, nature of the meeting (e.g., Kick-off meeting), duration and date, presenter.

Multimedia

If applicable and possible, all multimedia products will have this metadata at the end of the file.

CALL	Component 9 of the recovery and resilience plan
WORK PROGRAMME	Large projects for excellent researchers.
Project ID	09I03-03-V03-00008
Project web site	
Document type	Video, Digital story
Title	Establishing Slovakia's First Cutting-Edge Advanced Laser Tweezers Laboratory for In-Depth Analysis of Molecular Forces in Clinically Relevant Hsp70 clients
Authors	
Format	
Status of the document	Draft / Final version
Link	
Credits	

2.2 Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

In principle, most produced data will be openly available as the default, with two exceptions:

1. Research and other related data that can be a potential source of IPRs, as the public availability would jeopardize IPR evaluation processes, and
2. Internal communications with little relevance for outsiders. However, these data may be made available upon motivated request after anonymization.

A decision on whether particular data can be potentially used for IPR is solely on the researcher who conducted the experiment; if two and more researchers have participated in the experiment, a consensual decision has to be made.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g., by deposition in a repository)?

All ProteoForce data will be stored on the Zenodo repository. Before that moment, the data will be stored in the university servers and made accessible to members. Zenodo assigns a DOI to all documents uploaded and allows the storage of metadata.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g., in open source code)?

Most files will be accessible with general use software (word, excel, PowerPoint and their open versions). Successive versions of the DMP can be more specific for other types of data.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited?

Preference should be given to certified repositories that support open access where possible. All ProteoForce data will be stored on the Zenodo repository.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Yes

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

The restriction is foreseen only for data generated by the internal social tool used by researchers within their particular workspace. They will be released upon approval of the data producers.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No. Decision-making process for data access will be the competence of the project coordinator.

Are there well-described conditions for access (i.e., a machine-readable license)? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Conditions for the access will be specified in the next version of the DMP.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc. (i.e., adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

All metadata will refer to the Dublin Core. Moreover, we will make our metadata available following the OAI-PMH standard. The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability [3]. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP. OAI-PMH will come for free if the decision is made to exploit the ProteoForce Catalogue service provided by Zenodo.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

These are community-specific. A partial list of them should be included.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

This will be specified in the next version of the DMP.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

This will be specified in the next version of the DMP.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

ProteoForce reports will be licensed under Creative Commons license. The Creative Commons copyright licenses and tools forge a balance inside the traditional “all rights reserved” setting that copyright law creates. CC tools give everyone from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardized way to grant copyright permissions to creative work. The combination of CC tools and the users is

a vast and growing digital commons, a pool of content that can be copied, distributed, edited, remixed, and built upon, all within the boundaries of copyright law [4].

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

In general, data produced in the project will be made openly available as soon as the related deliverables are uploaded in the Project Portal.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Yes.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? Are data quality assurance processes described?

We expect that data remains re-usable. The data quality assurance process will be described in the next version of the DMP.

3. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

3.1 What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

To make data FAIR, Zenodo will be chosen as the central open access repository. However, we expect that some research publications can be selected to be published under the 'golden' option.

3.2 How will these be covered?

Costs for the making data FAIR will be covered from two possible resources: (1) other research grants (overheads/indirect costs/services), and (2) directly from the University (UPJS) budget.

3.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management is solved at the project operation level – WP1 Task 1.1 leader. ProteoForce staff will work closely with the dedicated Task leader.

3.4 Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

The resources for long-term data preservation are covered by the project coordinator.

4. DATA SECURITY

4.1 What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data are collected and stored in the ProteoForce workspace, and then data are sent to the Zenodo repository. This repository is protected with Transport Level Security (TLS) that offers communications security over the computer network. TLS guarantees privacy and data integrity between two communicating PC applications. In particular, any connections between a client (e.g., a web browser) and the ProteoForce workspace have the following properties:

- a. The connection is private (or secure) due to the adoption of symmetric cryptography to encrypt the data transmitted. The keys for this symmetric encryption are generated uniquely for each connection and are based on a shared secret negotiated at the start of the session. The server and client negotiate the details of which encryption algorithm and cryptographic keys to use before the first byte of data is transmitted. The negotiation of a shared secret is both secure (the negotiated secret is unavailable to eavesdroppers and cannot be obtained, even by an attacker who places themselves in the middle of the connection) and reliable (no attacker can modify the communications during the negotiation without being detected)
- b. The identity of the communicating parties can be authenticated using public-key cryptography. This authentication can be made optional at the client side but is ensured at the server-side
- c. The connection ensures integrity because each message transmitted includes a message integrity check using a message authentication code to prevent undetected loss or alteration of the data during transmission
- d. The connection ensures forward secrecy, ensuring that any future disclosure of encryption keys cannot be used to decrypt any TLS communications recorded in the past.

To protect ProteoForce data from various scenarios of data loss incidents, a backup and recovery strategy has been developed. The most probable data loss incidents can be divided into three categories [5]:

- 1) physical destruction of hardware such as server nodes and other related critical infrastructure due to *force majeure* or simply due to defective components
- 2) human error

3) viruses, malware, or ransomware

To prevent data loss incidents, such as that data are deleted accidentally, ProteoForce work package leaders are asked to keep the data copies using their individual storage modules or cloud systems. According to statistics, notebooks are less suitable for long-term storage [5].

The ProteoForce workspace provides continuous, online backup for data as a fully managed service. The service streams encrypted and compressed oplog data to a dedicated server so that a continuous backup is activated.

4.2 Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

5.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

According to the nature and scientific intent of the ProteoForce project, research activities involve natural and free-will collaboration with human beings/partners without the need to interfere or collect personal data and all information on collaborative partners are already publicly and officially available. Regarding the possible work and staff training involving strains of *Escherichia coli*, we will prepare health and safety procedures for the staff involved conforming to relevant local/national guidelines. The relevant document will be kept in a file and, upon request, submitted to the grant agency. During the implementation of specific project activities, especially task 1.3 *Laboratory installation and research of bio - constructs for optical tweezers*, and tasks Task 2.1. *Preparation and treatment of proteins for laser optical tweezers*, the participating persons will be trained and informed about the rules of safety and health protection at work.

6. FURTHER SUPPORT IN DEVELOPING YOUR DMP

The DMP will be updated based on *ad hoc* requirements collected during the project. Data management policies as defined in this version of the DMP will be evaluated by the project coordinator, who is also responsible for further development of a regular update of the DMP.

7. REFERENCES

[1] Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

[2] <https://www.dublincore.org/>

[3] <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

[4] <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

[5] <https://blog.storagecraft.com/data-loss-statistics-infographic>